

Koenigia lapathifolia, the Correct Name for *Koenigia alaskana* (Polygonaceae)

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER¹

Abstract—The combination *Koenigia alaskana* (Small) T.M.Schust. & Reveal is illegitimate because its basionym, *Polygonum alpinum alaskanum* Small, is a superfluous replacement name for *Polygonum alpinum* var. *lapathifolium* Cham. & Schltld. The correct combination, *Koenigia lapathifolia* (Cham. & Schltld.) M.van der Meer, is proposed.

Small (1895: 33) published *Polygonum alpinum alaskanum* as a replacement name for *Polygonum alpinum* var. *lapathifolium* Cham. & Schltld., apparently because he considered the latter name an illegitimate later homonym of *Polygonum lapathifolium* L.

However, under article 11.2 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (ICN; Turland & al. 2018), names have no priority outside the rank at which they are published. The limitation on this provision in article 53.3 is not applicable because it pertains only to subgeneric names and epithets below the rank of species. Hence, *Polygonum alpinum alaskanum* is an illegitimate later synonym of *Polygonum alpinum* var. *lapathifolium* and all combinations based on this basionym are also illegitimate.

¹ Roggekamp 379
NL-2592 VV Den Haag
m@vdm.nu
ORCID: 0000-0002-5182-9615

The correct combination in *Koenigia* L. is proposed here:

Koenigia lapathifolia (Cham. & Schltld.) M.van der Meer **comb. et stat. nov.**

- ≡ *Polygonum alpinum* var. *lapathifolium* Cham. & Schltld.
–Linnaea 3: 38 (1828)
- ≡ *Polygonum alpinum* [stat. indet.] *alaskanum* Small, nom. superfl.
- ≡ *Polygonum alpinum* var. *alaskanum* (Small) J.M.Macoun
- ≡ *Polygonum alpinum* subsp. *alaskanum* (Small) W.Wight ex Harshb.
- ≡ *Polygonum alaskanum* (Small) W.Wight
- ≡ *Koenigia alaskana* (Small) T.M.Schust. & Reveal
- ≡ *Aconogonon alaskanum* (Small) Soják

Koenigia lapathifolia* var. *glabrescens (Hultén) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**

- ≡ *Polygonum alaskanum* var. *glabrescens* Hultén
–Fl. Alaska Yukon 4 [in Acta Univ. Lund, 2, 40(1)]: 612 (1944)
- ≡ *Koenigia alaskana* var. *glabrescens* (Hultén) T.M.Schust. & Revea
- ≡ *Aconogonon alaskanum* var. *glabrescens* (Hultén) H.R.Hinds

Literature

Small J. K. (1895). A monograph of the North American species of the genus *Polygonum*. Memoirs from the Department of Botany of Columbia College, Vol. I. Lancaster, PA: The New Era Print.

<https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.15494>

Turland N. J., Wiersema J. H., Barrie F. R., Greuter W., Hawksworth D. L., Herendeen P. S., Knapp S., Kusber W.-H., Li D.-Z., Marhold K., May T. W., McNeill J., Monro A. M., Prado J., Price M. J. & Smith G. F. (eds.) (2018). International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code) adopted by the Nineteenth International Botanical Congress Shenzhen, China, July 2017. Regnum Vegetabile 159. Glashütten: Koeltz Botanical Books.

<https://doi.org/10.12705/Code.2018>